

TOURISM: A TOOL FOR RECREATIONAL ACTIVITY IN OYO STATE- NIGERIA: A CASE STUDY OF ADO AWAYE-SUSPENDED LAKE

¹Osuoha Ifeanyi Jude, ¹Akinmoyede Bolanle Florence, ¹Aina Stella Oluwatoyin Folajimi
and ²Nnamdi; Stanley Chibueze

Corresponding author: ifeanyi.osuoha@fuoye.edu.ng, +2348067116116

ORCID iD: 0009-0007-6913-6765

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Abstract

This study examines tourism as a recreational activity in Oyo State, Nigeria. The sampling method used was a non-probability sampling technique, and the type of non-probability sampling technique used was a simple random technique. The research design was through surveying and data collection was both qualitative and quantitative; therefore, both qualitative and quantitative data analysis were used as a result of the nature of variables involved. Cochran's equation of finite population $N_0 =$ was used to determine the sample of the study. The sampling method used was using a questionnaire. The primary data were determined with the aid of a questionnaire and were supplied by residents of the study areas. For quantitative analysis, the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS version 17) was used to process the data. A random sampling technique was adopted for data collection. To achieve the purpose of this study, two null hypotheses were developed and tested at a significance level of 0.05 using Spearman's rank correlation coefficient. A total of 150 questionnaires were distributed at the study location; only 143 (95.33%) questionnaires were recoverable while 7 (4.73%) questionnaires were not recovered. Based on the results of the analysis using data generated from the field with the instrument designed for the study, it can be concluded that the tourism potential of the Ado-Awaye suspended lake in Oyo state has a significant impact on the socio-cultural and economic development of Oyo state. Moreover, the mechanisms in place have a significant impact on the conservation of tourist attractions in Ado-Awaye's suspended lake in Oyo State.

¹Department of Hospitality and Tourism Management, Faculty of Agriculture, Federal University Oye-Ekiti, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

²Department of hospitality management technology, International Institute of Tourism and Hospitality, Yaenagoa, Bayelsa State, Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

Background of the study

The wide coverage of activities entailed in tourism, as well as its close interrelationship with cultural, social, economic, political, and environmental aspects of human life, adds to its conceptual broadness. The word 'tourist' comes from a French word 'touriste' meaning a person who, out of his/her own interest, undertakes a journey and, in the process, gets to know places outside his/her permanent place of abode during his/her free time. Free time is available on weekends, annual holidays, and public holidays and lasts for at least 24 hours. Tourists must not engage in paid work during such trips. Tourism, on the other hand, is a leisure activity in which people travel to destinations far away from where they usually live. They are often international in nature. According to Ijeoma and Enyangu (2014), tourism is a set of phenomena and relationships that arise from the travel and stay of non-residents, as it does not lead to permanent residence or is associated with any subsistence activities.

An increase in the human population and preferences for leisure activities often leads to an increase in the demand for recreational use of public lands in many parts of the world. According to Foot (2014), humans have unconsciously engaged in recreational activities since the ancient age when they wandered through dark virgin forests in search of light, shelter, and food to the Renaissance via modern searches for novelties and fun. As time continued, development and discoveries came up in leaps and bounds, causing the modern day planned fun-filled human activities. The development of these activities in conjunction with Western culture is what brings about tourism as it is today.

Akeredolu and Ayoola (2020) divided tourism into domestic and international tourism. According to them, domestic tourism refers to travel for recreational purposes that is intentionally carried out outside the tourist's place of residence within the national territory. International tourism can be divided into active and passive. Active tourism is associated with the arrival of foreign tourists to a country. These are foreign tourists who bring money to the country for tourism. Passive tourism refers to outbound tourists. This applies to people who travel abroad and bring foreign currency with them to their destination during their trip. It also categorizes tourism by location, targeting relatively pristine natural areas, such as protected areas and areas where the environment is intact, the climate is pleasant, natural resources are sustainable, and cultural diversity is preserved. The tourism that visitors visit is called "ecotourism". . ". Ecotourism is a form of tourism that involves visits to relatively fragile, undisturbed natural areas (environments) and is used as a low-cost, often small-scale, alternative to standard commercial tourism. Designed. The purpose may be to educate tourists and raise funds for environmental conservation, or for host communities to benefit directly from economic development and political empowerment. Therefore, this study investigates tourism as a recreational activity in Oyo State.

Statement of the Problems

This study is encompassed by numerous challenges such as the lack of appropriate promotional strategies for marketing potential tourist attractions. Lack of coordination between programs that promote and market tourism as well as attract tourist from far and near. Lack of conservative mechanisms, planning and management. Another problem that motivated this work is the paucity of literature on the socio-cultural and economic impact of tourism in Oyo State, as well as the lack of documentation of these natural and cultural attractions in the study areas.

Objectives of the study

The main purpose of the study is tourism as a recreational activity in Ado-Awaye Lake, Oyo State, Nigeria. The specific objectives are;

- examine the socio-cultural and economic impact of tourism at Ado-Awaye Lake in Oyo State on the people of Oyo State.

- to examine the conservation mechanisms in place for the conservation of tourist attractions in Ado-Awaye's suspended lake in Oyo State.

Research Questions

- i. What socio-cultural and economic impacts do tourism at Ado-Awaye Lake in Oyo State have on the people of Oyo State?
- ii. What conservation mechanisms are in place for the conservation of tourist attractions in Ado-Awaye, which has been suspended in Oyo State?

Research Hypothesis

For this study, the following hypotheses are developed to pilot the study.

H₁: The tourism potential of Ado-Awaye Lake in Oyo State has no significant impact on the sociocultural and economic development of the state.

H₀2: The mechanisms in place have no significant impact on the conservation of tourist attractions in the Ado-Awaye Suspended Lake in Oyo State.

LITERATURE REVIEW

This section discusses the conceptual framework and the theoretical and empirical review of the subject matter. The conceptual framework guides the study and summarizes the dependent and independent variables while conducting an empirical review of the previous research conducted by different authors on related topics, how the research was conducted, their observations, findings, and their recommendations.

Conceptual Literature

Definition of Tourism

Tourism is defined as travel for a limited time, usually for recreational, leisure, religious, family, or business purposes. Tourism is usually associated with traveling abroad; however, it can also refer to traveling to different parts of the country. Tourism is the collection of activities, services, and industries that provide travel experiences, including transportation, accommodation, restaurants and eateries, and retail establishments provided to individuals or groups traveling away from home. Entertainment businesses, recreational facilities, and other hospitality services. Ladan (2003) defined it as the sum of phenomena and relationships that arise from the travel and stay of nonresidents. This is because these do not lead to permanent residence. Egbaji (2007) defined tourism as the science, art, and business of attracting, transporting, welcoming visitors, and graciously meeting their needs and desires. Other authorities have expanded the scope of this definition. For example, Egbaji (2007) defines it as a strange service discipline that emphasizes movements aimed at changing everyday life. Agbat al. (2010) viewed tourism as a commercial organization that provides places and activities for people to indulge in during their holidays. Tourism was initially considered a source of recreation and tourism. The fact that tourism improves social relations means that it can influence people's attitudes and behaviors and, in turn, influence social change. Furthermore, Eja, Smith, and Adebajo (2011) explained that tourism is a comprehensive concept, including the interaction of other factors such as transportation, communication, accommodation, and destination. Tourism refers to traveling for leisure, business, or pleasure. People who participate in this activity are called tourists. Akpet (2005) defined tourists as people who travel and stay in places outside their usual environment for up to a year at a time for leisure, business, or other purposes.

Tourism in Nigeria

Tourism in Nigeria focuses primarily on cultural events because of the large number of ethnic groups in the country, but it also includes rainforests, savannahs, waterfalls, and other natural attractions. In recent times, governments at both federal and state levels have had a significant impact on tourism development, either exclusively or in some cases in collaboration with the private sector, regarding resorts of international standards specializing in attraction tourism. (Gustafson, 2012). According to Ayamenhue (2010), there is no doubt that Nigeria's tourism potential is huge and, if properly developed, will generate huge revenues for the country.

Nigeria has vast, wide-open river and ocean beaches perfect for swimming and other water sports, unique wildlife, vast areas of unspoiled nature ranging from tropical rainforests, spectacular waterfalls, and rapid It has a wide range of tourist attractions, including a growing emerging city and climatic conditions. Some regions of the country are particularly suitable for relaxation. Other attractions include weather, climate, vegetation, quality airspace, sunshine, spectacular landscapes, cliffs, waterfalls, enchanting beaches, historical ruins, rich cultural diversity, friendly people and wildlife. animals, Nigeria's tourism assets; and locally preserved traditional ways of life. , the rich and diverse range of handicrafts and other colorful items depict and portray the local art and way of life, as well as the authentic, rustic, and friendly attitude of many Nigerian people.

This makes Nigeria one of Africa's leading tourist havens. The World Trade Organization (WTO, 2014) stated that the tourism and hospitality industry is one of Africa's largest assets but the least invested, with a market value of \$50 billion, four times the current level.^{2,037} He pointed out that there is \$1 billion in untapped potential. . The agency's forecast for international tourist arrivals to Africa stated that 77.3 million people will travel to Africa in 2020. This corresponds to an annual growth rate of 5.5% per decade, which is faster than the global growth rate of 4.1%. Other countries estimate that Africa, together with Asia, will account for more than half of the expected increase in international visitor numbers, with 30% of this increase expected worldwide. Similarly, the United Nations in 2013 said, "Traveling and tourism to the world economy reached 7 billion, accounted for 9.5 % of the world GDP, and is faster than other important sectors." It has been reported. Commercial financial, finance, transportation and production commercial services. one of the 11 new works created around the world belongs to sightseeing (Gustafson, 2012). In addition, more and more countries use industries, and as the number of accommodated investments increases, the number of tourist destinations in the world is increasing to turn tourism into an important engine for social progress and export through the creation of workplaces. Please note that the file is open. Development of income from foreign tourists and infrastructure (WTTC, 2014, 2015). It also predicts that "the number of international tourists is expected to increase by 3.3% over the next 15 years, reaching 1.8 billion by 2030."

In Nigeria, the economic impact of revenue exports from international tourism spending is expected to increase total annual revenue by US\$224 million (US\$29 billion). Furthermore, we are not losing market share in emerging countries. From 30% in 1980 to 47% in 2015 and by 2030 he is expected to reach 57% by 2030, which corresponds to more than 1 billion international tourists. To do. Term Agreement between the United Nations and the WTO). The tourism forecast period ends in 2030.

Today, tourism is no longer a leisure activity, but it has attracted the attention of economists as a major source of foreign exchange for developing and developed countries. Ambiguous countries are seeking to develop both tourist destinations, standardize their operations, and We are forced to improve infrastructure such as airports. Railroad. Roads, and ports that support tourism. On the other hand, unlike oil, which is non-renewable and employs less than 2% of the population at best, tourism is an inclusive, sustainable, labor-intensive industry that employs both skilled and unskilled workers. It can create more jobs per unit of investment than the oil industry. From an environmental perspective, tourism, if properly developed and managed, can help preserve the natural environment, historic, archeological and religious sites, and promote the use of local culture, folklore, traditions, art, and culture. It can act as a mechanism to protect ecosystems such as crafts and cooking. Gustafsson, 2012). From an economic perspective, tourism benefits federal, state, and local governments through revenue generation, foreign exchange and return on investment, taxation of tourists and tourism products, and linkages with other local industries, such as agriculture. This brings many benefits not only to municipalities but also to the private sector. Furthermore, The scope of tourism employment is not limited to urban areas; it also extends to rural areas with tourist attractions and monuments (Gustafson, 2012).

Tourism potential in Nigeria

It is a common phenomenon that the availability of tourism products and services and the abundance of tourist destinations stimulate the development of tourism in any country. In this regard, Nigeria has rich tourism components that could make it a major tourism provider in Africa. There is very much to offer, from beautiful

natural places to cultural and historical heritage. Other components of tourism in Nigeria include transportation, accommodation, leisure, and entertainment (Adora, 2010).

Tourist Attractions in Nigeria

From the spiritual splendor of ancient northern cities to the delta region to the Yoruba kingdom, to the breathtaking natural environment of Igbo Island and many pure landscapes. Every visitor to Nigeria holds their breath with anticipation and excitement (Adora, 2010). Some tourist centers in this country are listed below.

Ikogosi warm and cold spring resort, Ekiti, Japan

Ikogosi Spa Resort is one of the most beautiful natural resources in Nigeria. The water flows over the hills, where the hot springs combine with other cold springs from the surrounding hills to form a continuous stream with a temperature of 70 degrees. Located in western Nigeria, known as Ekiti State, Ikogosi is a small community in terms of size and population. The community is an essential element of modern tourism. Ikogosi has a good local natural environment, combined with a rich culture and history, which is the basis for making this community a tourist destination (Adora, 2010).

Calabar, a tourist destination

Calabar is one of the most attractive tourist destinations in Nigeria. Being the capital of the Cross River State, there are many things to see in terms of tourism. One of Calabar’s tourist attractions is its colonial architecture in its oldest part. Talking about Calabar as a tourist destination without talking about Obudu Mountain Resort is like a Christmas without snow. Obudu Resort provides complete satisfaction to both leisure and business travelers. One of the main attractions of Obudu Resort is its mountain setting. It is on a plateau at an altitude of 1,576 m on the Oshie ridge of the Sankwala Mountains. These climatic conditions are perfect for a perfect respite from Africa’s tropical heat. The atmosphere, favorable weather conditions, and breathtaking views make this an ideal tourist destination for leisure and business travelers, adventurers, families, couples, and tour groups (Adora, 2010).

Conceptual Framework

Independent variables

Tourism and Ecotourism

- Ambience Conditions
- Ecological view
- Natural Esthetics of the study area

Dependent variables

Tourism Potential

- Revenue Generation
- Increase in Tourist Visitations
- Job Creation
- Infrastructural Development
- Rich Cultural Heritage and
- Diversity Conservation of Cultural Heritage

Tourism potential of ecotourism

Revenue Generation

Revenue generated from tourists’ visits to the site remains the most obvious economic benefit of ecotourism. Revenue generation can be from domestic sources or earnings in foreign exchange, in which case it involves visits by nationals of other countries.

Job Creation

The establishment and management of ecotourism centers like Ado-Awaye Hanging Lake will provide many job opportunities for unemployed Nigerian youths. The jobs will not be limited to tourism sites and their

facilities, but will also allow for the development of tourism-allied industries and services that will engage a good number of skilled and unskilled hands. Direct employment within the tourism site will involve personnel in various positions, such as tourism management and administration, field supervision, tour guidance, souvenir vending, and security management. Activities of service providers in sectors such as transportation, accommodation and hospitality, entertainment, and other tourism-related industries will also provide jobs. The cumulative effect of direct and indirect jobs from tourism and associated service providers will help reduce the nation's unemployment rate. In cases where tourism sites are located in rural areas, rural–urban migration reduces and aids the decongestion of urban centers. Youth engagement through job creation will reduce poverty levels and raise the standard of living in many households (Esu, 2015).

Infrastructural Development

For ecotourism to achieve its optimal potential, the development of infrastructure in host communities with natural endowments is very important, irrespective of the community's rural or urban nature. In addition to basic facilities put in place by tourism-associated service providers, infrastructures such as roads, railways, seaports and airports, potable water, power, telecommunication facilities, entertainment centers, and shopping malls provide comfort and serve as attractions to tourists (Ashley, Boyd, and Goodwin, 2000). In addition, infrastructural development will reduce the level of restiveness among Nigerian youths.

Rich Cultural Heritage and Diversity

Tourism provides points of contact among people from different sociocultural backgrounds. The program allows for an exhibition of the cultural values of host communities in areas such as the local language, traditions, music, arts and artifacts, religion, history, dressing style, education systems, and local leisure activities. In addition to cultural dilution, tourism will allow for showcasing the rich sociocultural values of Nigerian ethnic groups in host communities where the tourist attractions are located.

Conservation of Cultural Heritage

The development of ecotourism features in the host community will encourage the conservation of cultural heritage through the economic benefits derived from tourism activities. Among the Yorubas, annual festivals such as Eyo, Egungun, and Ojude-Oba celebrations are examples of cultural heritage that can be added to tourism products under exploitation. The participation of tourists in such traditional events, especially those that provide economic benefits and regeneration of traditional arts and crafts, will help to revitalize native cultures and ensure the continued preservation of cultural heritage.

Stimulating recreational and educational values

Ecotourism stimulates the establishment of various outdoor and indoor recreational activities. Sporting activities, such as swimming, beach soccer, beach volleyball, and boat racing, have been developed to maximize the use of coastal and marine tourism centers. Indoor games such as table tennis, tennis, card games, local games such as “Ayo Olopon,” local music, and dances can be integrated into tourism products as additional recreational activities. Learning skills in local arts and exchange of ideas between members of host communities and tourists will result in improved technical knowledge for both parties. The influx of tourists from local and international communities will also motivate Nigerian youth to acquire educational values and skills. This will not only increase the literacy level of the citizenry but also improve their human capacity (Adora, 2010)

Empirical Literature

Olaniyi and Bada (2020) studied whether the location of Ad Away Hanging Lake (ASL) and its surroundings in Nigeria are suitable for mountain tourism. The AHP results showed that slope and roughness had the highest weights (27.87%) and maximum precipitation had the lowest weight (4.05%). The majority of ASL (117.05 hectares, or 61.40%) is confined to frontline rural areas and is suitable for tourism activities and development.

The smallest part (0.18 ha, 0.10%) was found to contribute to tourism activities and development related to remote areas. However, it was concluded that although ASL has a wealth of ecotourism attractions, inadequate support facilities and poor maintenance exist to enhance the experience and satisfaction of mountain tourists. Very suitable for nature-oriented activities such as camping, hiking, learning local/ethnic culture, wildlife observation, and nature photography. Therefore, relevant authorities and other key stakeholders should adopt the location suitability model to plan and develop mountain tourism in the ASL region.

Okosun (2020) assessed stakeholder perceptions of the Old Oyo National Park in Nigeria. Research has shown that Old Oyo National Park is an attractive tourist destination. However, although the park is fairly well maintained, public awareness of the tourism center is relatively low. The results show that local residents blame the government for the lack of park development and public awareness. The study also found that parks have a positive impact on local communities. Some of the main issues identified were inadequate management of the existing facilities. The study recommended maintenance of facilities, transportation improvements and public-private partnerships for the development of this national park. Meseko et al. (2018) investigated the tourism potential of the confluence of the Niger and Benue rivers in Nigeria: Implications for project funding. The study found that applying the project financing model of management and expropriation contracts increases the feasibility of tourism investments in Lokoja. This study showed that the confluence of the Niger and Benue rivers can be developed based on the above method, and the project could bring significant benefits to tourists, investors, and the government. Ajulo et al. (2017) assessed the tourism potential of two waterfalls in southwestern Nigeria. The investigation revealed that both sites had reception facilities. Recreation center, tight security, guest house near Olumirin Falls, gift shop where you can buy drinks and toiletries, unfinished restaurant, good road to Alinta Falls. From this study, these two sites had a very low level of development but still generated revenue for the state. If you are careful, you can even make progress over time. The study concluded that if these types of tourism facilities are properly maintained, they will generate additional revenue for the states in which they reside (Osun and Ekiti) and increase the intrastate income generated (IGR). Therefore, this study recommends that the state government should pay attention to these tourist destinations and make them world-class tourist destinations that attract tourists from all over the world.

Theoretical Literature

The theories adjudged to be useful for this study are functionalism theory and Modernization theory.

Functionalism

Functionalism is a mode of analysis used particularly in the social sciences, which purports to explain social and cultural phenomena in terms of their functions in sociocultural systems (Hunter and White, 1976). In other words, functionalism is concerned with the function of a component in a system. Okeibunor and Anugwom (2005) also took the same view. In their opinion functionalism “is the contribution that an institution or item or any partial activity makes to the maintenance of the whole”. They further stated that the fundamental theoretical premise of functionalism is based on Durkheim’s hypothesis of social solidarity.

Therefore, functionalism’s basic question is “How does society meet its needs? Each process, institution and practice is seen as performing a function that meets a societal need and helps maintain society’s structure or equilibrium. In other words, processes and institutions are understood in terms of their contribution to the ongoing social life (Mann, 1992).

Hence, the basic tenet of the functionalist approach is that societies are conceived as systems of mutually interdependent parts, and therefore no single institution can be understood isolated from the cultural whole. In this way, the tourism industry cannot be understood outside the industrial/cultural sector, where its role can be assessed.

Another central element of functionalist theory is the assumption that social systems must meet certain needs or 'necessary conditions of existence' or functional imperatives if society is to survive (Hunter and White, 1976). Radcliffe (1952) expresses this proposition by drawing an analogy between biological organisms and social systems. Just as the life of an organism is maintained by the activities of particular cells, fluids, and organs, the social system is maintained by the proper functioning of its constituent institutions. In this vein the Nigeria cultural resources would be maintained following the proper functioning of all its sectors. For instance, a sole dependence on the art and culture sector might be catastrophic when cultural resources are well maintained. Of course, one of the features of a system stressed by functionalists is its tendency toward equilibrium or balance among its parts and among the forces operating on it. Changes in one institution have implications for other institutions and for the community or society as a whole, with adaptation being a continuous process. For example, changes in tourism potential (natural and cultural) may cause a slight change or total change in the tourism industry.

Theoretical Orientation

The theoretical orientation of harnessing tourism potential can be described as a framework that focuses on identifying and understanding the factors that contribute to the success of a destination's tourism industry. The proposed framework includes several key elements:

- **Market research and analysis:** Understanding tourists' needs and wants, as well as the strengths and weaknesses of the destination.
- **Product development:** Designing and developing products and services that meet tourists' needs.
- **Promotion and marketing:** Creating and implementing strategies to attract tourists to the destination.
- **Policy and regulation:** Creating policies and regulations that support and encourage tourism development.

Market research and analysis: This involves gathering information about tourists' needs and wants, as well as the competitive landscape in the destination. It is important to understand what tourists are looking for and what they value in a travel experience.

Product development: This involves creating products and services that meet tourists' needs. This could include developing new attractions, creating marketing materials, or improving the quality of existing products and services.

Promotion and marketing: This involves creating and implementing strategies to promote the destination to potential tourists.

Policy and regulation: This involves creating policies and regulations that support and encourage tourism development. This could include tax incentives, marketing grants, and infrastructure investments. It is important to create fair policies and consistent and that do not create barriers to tourism development.

Destination management: This involves coordinating all elements of tourism development to ensure that the destination operates smoothly. This could include managing visitor numbers, ensuring adequate infrastructure, and responding to crises.

METHODOLOGY

The population of the study included residents living west of Iseyin, the Iseyin Local Government Area of Oyo State. The sampling method used is a non-probability sampling technique, and the type of non-probability sampling technique used is a simple random technique. The research design is a survey method and data collection is both qualitative and quantitative; therefore, both qualitative and quantitative data analysis will be used because of the nature of the variables involved.

Cochran's equation for a finite population was used to determine the study sample. The formula is as follows:

$$N_0 = \frac{Z^2 pq}{e^2 N}$$

$$N_0 = \frac{SS}{1 + \frac{SS-1}{Pop}}$$

Where

SS = Sample size

Pop = population.

; n = sample size

Z = Z value of confidence level.

P = Estimated proportion of an attribute present in the population.

q = 1-p.

e = Desired level of precision expressed in decimal.

N = population size.

Using a 90% confidence interval; Z = 1.645)

e = ± 10% = 0.1

p = 0.5 (maximum variable)

q = 1- 0.5 = 0.5

N = 0.5.

$$N_0 = \frac{(1.645)^2(0.5)(0.5)}{(0.10)^2} = \mathbf{160}$$

$$N_0 = \frac{160}{1 + \frac{(160-1)}{4300}} = 153.85 \text{ } \mathbf{\Omega} \mathbf{150}$$

The sampling procedure, which involves selecting residential divisions, was performed using a simple random procedure.

The validity test of the instrument helps the researcher assess the value of particular methods, results, and conclusion of a study and for making a self-assessment of one's personal work.

Reliability work includes elements of consistency in the measures and facts presented. Two questions are suggested to guide researchers in establishing the reliability of the referred materials. The following questions were asked:

- i. would the method adopted, if repeated by a different researcher at the same time or by the same person at a later time, yield the same results as the second one?
- ii. are the results reproducible under other circumstances?

Only when the above questions are answered can an instrument be considered reliable. Validity is used as a test of the data collection method. Here too, the questions below should guide one in the collection as well as in examining the quality of works reviewed: does the researcher obtain measurements of what they are really trying to measure?

Spearman's ranking correlation coefficient was used to analyze the relationship between the potential of Ado-Away Hanging Lake in Oyo State and tourism development in Nigeria. The technique was used because; the data analyzed was quantitative, and quantitative data can take exact numerical values, adequate sample size at least 10, one or more categories, independent observation, data presented in frequency form, and all the observations were used.

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, AND RESULTS

This section compiles and organizes the report of the data collected from the sampled respondents based on the research purpose and objectives. Presentation, analysis, and interpretation of tourism as a recreational activity of Ado-Away Lake in Oyo State, Nigeria. 4.1 Section A: Assessment of the sociocultural and economic impacts of tourism at Ado-Aaye Lake on Oyo State Tourism

Table 1: Respondents' knowledge about whether Ado-Away's suspended lake can promote the rich cultural heritage and diversity of the State**The Ado-Away Suspended Lake can promote the rich cultural heritage and diversity of the state.**

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	61	42.66
Agree	43	30.07
Disagree	28	19.58
Strongly Disagree	11	7.69
Total	143	100%

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Table 1 shows respondents' views on the notion that Ado-Away's suspended lake can promote the rich cultural heritage and diversity of the State. 42.66% (61) of the respondents strongly agreed, 30.07% (43) agreed, 19.58% (28) of the respondents disagreed, while the remaining 7.69% (11) of the respondents strongly disagreed. The majority of respondents strongly agreed, indicating that the Ado-Away Suspended Lake can promote the rich cultural heritage and diversity of the State.

Table 2: Respondents' knowledge about whether Ado-Away's suspended lake can enhance the conservation of the cultural heritage of the State**The Ado-Away Suspended Lake can enhance the conservation of the cultural heritage of the State**

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	58	40.56
Agree	41	28.67
Disagree	29	20.28
Strongly Disagree	15	10.49
Total	143	100%

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Table 2 shows respondents' views on the notion that Ado-Away's suspended lake can enhance the conservation of the cultural heritage of the State. 40.56% (58) of the respondents strongly agreed, 28.67% (41) agreed, 20.28% (29) of the respondents disagreed, while the remaining 10.49% (15) of the respondents strongly disagreed. The majority of respondents strongly agreed that the Ado-Away Suspended Lake can enhance the conservation of the cultural heritage of the State.

Table 3: Respondents' knowledge about whether Ado-Away's suspended lake can stimulate recreational and educational values of the State**The Ado-Away Suspended Lake can stimulate the recreational and educational values of the state.**

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	58	40.56
Agree	47	32.87
Disagree	21	14.69
Strongly Disagree	17	11.89
Total	143	100%

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Table 3 shows respondents' views on the notion that Ado-Away's suspended lake can stimulate recreational and educational values of the State. 40.56% (58) of the respondents strongly agreed, 32.87% (47) agreed, 14.69% (21) disagreed, and the remaining 11.89% (17) strongly disagreed. The majority of respondents strongly agreed that the Ado-Away Suspended Lake can stimulate the recreational and educational values of the State.

Table 4: Respondents' knowledge about whether Ado-Away's suspended lake can meet the needs of tourists and the State while maintaining and enhancing future opportunities.

The Ado-Away Suspended Lake can meet the needs of tourists and the State while maintaining and enhancing future opportunities.		
Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	65	45.46
Agree	43	30.07
Disagree	29	20.28
Strongly Disagree	6	4.20
Total	143	100%

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Table 4 shows respondents' views on the notion that Ado-Away's suspended lake can meet the needs of tourists and the State while maintaining and enhancing future opportunities. 45.46% (65) of the respondents strongly agreed, 30.07% (43) agreed, 20.28% (29) disagreed, and the remaining 4.20% (16) strongly disagreed. The majority of respondents strongly agreed that the Ado-Away Suspended Lake can meet the needs of tourists and the State while maintaining and enhancing future opportunities.

Table 5: Respondents' knowledge about whether Ado-Away's suspended lake can positively impact the economic and social welfare of the State while maintaining cultural integrity.

The Ado-Away-Suspended Lake can have a positive impact on the economic and social welfare of the State while maintaining cultural integrity.		
Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	75	52.45
Agree	33	23.08
Disagree	21	14.69
Strongly Disagree	14	9.79
Total	143	100%

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Table 5 shows respondents' views on the notion that Ado-Away's suspended lake can positively impact the economic and social welfare of the State while maintaining cultural integrity. 52.45% (75) of the respondents strongly agreed, 23.08% (33) agreed, 14.69% (21) disagreed, and the remaining 9.79% (14) strongly disagreed. The majority of respondents strongly agreed, indicating that the Ado-Away Suspended Lake can positively impact the economic and social welfare of the State while maintaining cultural integrity.

Section B: Assessment of the Conservation Mechanisms for the Conservation of Tourist Attractions in the Ado-Away Suspended Lake of Oyo State

Table 6: Respondents' knowledge about whether regularization and monitoring pollution helps develop resources at Ado-Away's suspended lake.

Regularization and monitoring of pollution helps develop resources at the Ado-Away Dam.		
Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	52	36.36
Agree	71	49.65
Disagree	7	4.90
Strongly Disagree	13	9.09
Total	143	100%

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Table 6 shows respondents' views on whether regularization and monitoring of pollution helps in the development of the resources at Ado-Away Suspended Lake. 36.36% (52) of the respondents strongly agreed, 49.65% (71) agreed, 4.90% (7) of the respondents disagreed, and the remaining 9.09% (13) of the respondents

strongly disagreed. The majority of respondents agreed, indicating that regularization and monitoring of pollution helps in the development of resources at Ado-Away's suspended lake.

Table 7: Respondents' knowledge about whether the development of adequate infrastructure in Ado-Away Suspended Lake can develop its tourism resource.

The development of adequate infrastructure in Ado-Away Suspended Lake will improve its tourism resources

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	53	37.06
Agree	60	41.96
Disagree	14	9.79
Strongly Disagree	16	11.19
Total	143	100%

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Table 7 shows respondents' views on whether the development of adequate infrastructure in Ado-Away Suspended Lake develops its tourism resource. 37.06% (53) of the respondents strongly agreed, 41.96% (60) agreed, 9.79% (14) disagreed, and the remaining 11.19% (16) strongly disagreed. The majority of respondents agreed, affirming that the development of adequate infrastructure in Ado-Away Suspended Lake has developed its tourism resource.

Table 8: Respondents' knowledge about whether establishing rules and regulations is one way of developing tourism resources in Ado-Away's suspended lake.

Establishing rules and regulations for high standards is one way to develop tourism resources in Ado-Away's suspended lake.

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	69	48.25
Agree	55	38.46
Disagree	9	6.29
Strongly Disagree	10	6.99
Total	143	100%

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Table 8 shows respondents' views on whether establishing rules and regulations of high standards is one way of developing the tourism resource in Ado-Away Suspended Lake. A total of 48.25% (69) of the respondents strongly agreed, 38.46% (55) agreed, 6.29% (9) disagreed, and the remaining 6.99% (10) disagreed. The majority of respondents strongly agreed, indicating that establishing rules and regulations of high standards is one way of developing tourism resources in Ado-Away.

Table 9: Respondents' knowledge about whether the eradication of illegal activities at Ado-Away Suspended Lake increases the chances of developing its tourism resource.

Eradicating illegal activities at the Ado-Away Suspended Lake increases the potential for developing tourism resources.

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	57	39.86
Agree	43	30.07
Disagree	18	12.59
Strongly Disagree	25	17.48
Total	143	100%

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Table 9 shows respondents' views on whether the eradication of illegal activities at Ado-Awaye Suspended Lake increases the chances of developing its tourism resource. 39.86% (57) of the respondents strongly agreed, 30.07% (43) agreed, 12.59% (18) disagreed, and the remaining 17.48% (25) strongly disagreed. The majority of respondents strongly agreed; this affirms that the eradication of illegal activities at Ado-Awaye Suspended Lake increases the chances of developing its tourism resource.

Table 10: Respondents' knowledge about whether proper management and policy making to help reduce over-congestion is one way to develop the tourism resource at Ado-Awaye Suspended Lake.

Proper management and policymaking to help reduce over-congestion is one way to develop tourism resources in Ado-Awaye.		
Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	58	40.56
Agree	47	32.87
Disagree	23	16.08
Strongly Disagree	15	10.49
Total	143	100%

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Table 10 shows respondents' views on the notion that proper management and policy making to help reduce over-congestion is one way of developing the tourism resource at Ado-Awaye Suspended Lake. 40.56% (58) of the respondents strongly agreed, 32.87% (47) agreed, 16.08% (23) of the respondents disagreed, while the remaining 10.49% (15) of the respondents strongly disagreed. The majority of respondents strongly agreed, indicating that proper management and policymaking to help reduce over-congestion is one way to develop the tourism resource at Ado-Awaye Suspended Lake.

Hypothesis Testing

❖ **Null hypothesis:** The tourism potential of Ado-Awaye Lake in Oyo State has no significant impact on the sociocultural and economic development of the state.

Variables	ΣX	ΣX²	ΣY²	ΣXY	r-val
Tourist Potential of Ado-Awaye's Suspended Lake	699	3189		5674	0.78
Tourism, sociocultural, and economic development in Oyo State	184	2815			

Significant 0.05, critical r = 0.178, df =498.

From the results presented in Table A, the calculated r-value of 0.78 is higher than the critical r-value of 0.178 at 0.05 levels of significance and 498 degrees of freedom. The null hypothesis was rejected, while the alternate hypothesis, which stated that the tourism potential of Ado-Awaye's suspended lake in Oyo State has a significant impact on the socio-cultural and economic development of Oyo State, was accepted.

Conclusions

Testing hypothesis 1 on the tourism potential of Ado-Awaye's suspended lake in Oyo State has a significant impact on the socio-cultural and economic development of Oyo State, the majority of respondents strongly agreed, indicating that the lake can promote the rich cultural heritage and diversity of the State. The Ado-Awaye Suspended Lake can enhance the conservation of the cultural heritage of the State. The Ado-Awaye Suspended Lake can stimulate the recreational and educational values of the State. The Ado-Awaye Suspended

Lake can meet the needs of tourists and the State while maintaining and enhancing future opportunities. The Ado-Awaye-Suspended Lake can have a positive impact on the economic and social welfare of the State while maintaining cultural integrity.

Hypothesis two analyzed whether the mechanisms in place have a significant impact on the conservation of tourist attractions in Ado-Awaye, which is a suspended lake in Oyo State. The majority of respondents agreed, indicating that regularization and monitoring of pollution helps in the development of resources at Ado-Awaye's suspended lake. The development of adequate infrastructure in Ado-Awaye Suspended Lake has developed its tourism resources. Establishing rules and regulations for high standards is one way to develop the tourism resource in Ado-Awaye Suspended Lake. the eradication of illegal activities at Ado-Awaye Suspended Lake increases the chances of developing its tourism resource. Also, proper management and policymaking to help reduce over-congestion is one way to develop the tourism resources at Ado-Awaye's suspended lake. These findings are in agreement with the empirical work of Okosun (2020), which assessed stakeholders' perceptions of Old Oyo National Park, Nigeria. The research revealed that the Park has positively influenced the community's development.

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATION

Summary

Tourism development has a long way to go. Although Oyo State has some of the best natural resources for tourism, there is a need to develop all tourist destinations in the state. In states like Cross River, Lagos, and Plateau, the provision of tourist facilities within a destination site, such as communication, security, accommodation, and transportation, was given adequate attention.

This study has therefore to a great extent expressed Ado-Awaye's Suspended Lake in Oyo State as a natural attraction with a view to offering possible strategic plans and harness for sustainable tourism development and promotion in Oyo State in particular and the nation at large.

Conclusion

The study concludes that the tourism potential of the Ado-Awaye suspended lake in Oyo state has a significant impact on the socio-cultural and economic development of the state. Moreover, the mechanisms in place have a significant impact on the conservation of tourist attractions in Ado-Awaye's suspended lake in Oyo State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following

- ❖ The Oyo State Ministry of Information, Culture, and Tourism and other tourism organizations should carry out public awareness campaigns on the benefits of ecotourism to Ado-Awaye Suspended Lake and other ecotourism endowed communities to encourage their participation in ecotourism ventures. This will create the needed awareness of the usefulness of ecotourism and the advantages of ecotourism over other forms of tourism. This will enhance community participation in ecotourism activities.
- ❖ Regular monitoring and supervision of tourism activities and development should be implemented to supervise ecotourist activities to enhance environmental sustainability.

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